

Perspectives of Journalists in Ilorin on the Implications of Artificial Intelligence for Broadcasting Industry in Kwara State

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17260374>

Abstract

This paper examined the adaptive strategies available to journalists amid rapid technological advancements. This paper adopted unified theory of acceptance and use of technology as theoretical framework to provide a unified understanding of the key determinants that influence individuals' intentions and behaviours concerning the adoption of new technologies. The paper adopted a qualitative research design. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews with purposively selected broadcast journalists based on their experiences and engagements with AI tools in media work. Thematic analysis was employed to identify recurring patterns, shared concerns and divergent views among participants. Findings revealed that while AI enhances efficiency and introduces innovative storytelling methods, it also raises significant concerns about journalistic ethics, credibility, and potential deskilling. Journalists expressed worries about overreliance on technology, erosion of investigative depth, and shifting professional roles. Participants emphasised the need for continuous upskilling and a shift toward more analytical and interpretive journalism in response to AI integration. The study concluded that journalists in Ilorin perceive AI as both a transformative tool and a professional threat. It recommended the development of national policies to guide the ethical use of AI in journalism and the implementation of regular training programmes to help journalists remain relevant in a rapidly evolving media landscape.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Journalism, Broadcasting Industry, Ethics, Newsroom Automation

Introduction

Broadcast media have long served as a vital conduit between the public and their environment, fulfilling its core functions of education, entertainment, and information dissemination (Qin, 2021). These roles have enabled broadcasting to remain a central force in shaping public discourse and societal awareness. The endurance of broadcast media can largely be attributed to the adaptability and resilience of broadcasters, who continue to innovate and tailor content delivery to meet evolving audience demands (Punchihewa, 2018).

Since Guglielmo Marconi pioneered radio broadcasting in 1895 and the subsequent launch of the first commercial radio station in the United States, the industry has undergone significant evolution. One of the most notable milestones in this trajectory has been the transition from analogue to digital broadcasting. The incorporation of digital

technologies, such as transmitters, tricastors, teleprompters, wirecast systems, and studio automation tools, has significantly enhanced the efficiency and scope of media production and distribution. Nevertheless, the pace of this digital transformation varies widely across nations, with some achieving full digital integration, while others continue to struggle with infrastructural and policy limitations (Nsude, 2022).

Amid this broader digital shift, the world is now firmly in the grip of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which is marked by quick progress in technologies like AI, robots, machine learning and the internet of Things (IoT) and expert systems. AI, in particular, has found applications across multiple sectors, including healthcare, education, commerce, finance, and more recently, journalism (Ayantade, 2022). Scholars have argued that the survival and competitiveness of any industry, including media, will increasingly depend on its ability to adopt and adapt to these transformative technologies (de-Lima-Santhos & Ceron, 2022).

In the context of journalism, AI is changing the way news is collected, produced and distributed. While these innovations promise increased efficiency and new storytelling techniques, they also raise critical concerns about editorial independence, ethical standards, job security, and the redefinition of journalistic roles. De-Lima-Santos & Mesquita (2021a) say that the prospects of journalism and its financial models depends a lot on how much technology is used, the study therefore determined Perspectives of Journalists in Ilorin on the Implications of Artificial Intelligence for Broadcasting Industry in Kwara State.

Statement of Problem

In Nigeria, the broadcasting sector faces unique challenges amid the twin pressures of digitisation. In cities such as Ilorin, broadcast journalists serve as vital actors in the public information ecosystem, responsible for informing citizens and holding power to account. However, the increasing deployment of AI technologies introduces both opportunities and threats, particularly regarding job displacement, ethical dilemmas, and shifts in professional identity.

Although prior studies have examined AI's role in Nigerian journalism, such as the work of Okiyi & Nsude (2021), which explored the adoption of AI in journalistic practice from a conceptual standpoint, there remains a need for empirical, context-specific investigations that capture the lived experiences and perspectives of broadcast journalists on the ground.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Explore the perspectives of broadcast journalists on the potential impact of AI in news gathering and reportage within the broadcasting industry.
2. Investigate journalists' concerns about AI's capacity to replace human labour or compromise journalistic ethics.
3. Identify the perceived benefits and drawbacks of AI on journalistic roles and workflows in Ilorin.
4. Evaluate the adaptive strategies and options available to practising journalists based on adoption of AI in Nigerian media.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is widely considered as the capacity of digital computers systems to operate tasks typically requiring human intelligence (Copeland, 2021). These tasks include reasoning, interpreting meaning, generalising from data, and learning from previous experiences. In essence, AI refers to efforts aimed at replicating human cognitive abilities within machines.

Despite rapid advancements in processing power and data storage, AI systems still fall short of replicating the full spectrum of human flexibility, particularly in areas requiring common sense and broad contextual understanding (Galily, 2018). However, in narrowly defined domains, AI has demonstrated capabilities that exceed those of human specialists. Such applications include medical diagnostics, search engine algorithms, voice recognition systems, and handwriting analysis (Godswill & Ifeyinma, 2019).

Ajayi (2018) identifies several key AI technologies that are increasingly influential across various sectors. These are methods such as natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition, machine learning, deep learning platforms, biometrics, automated robot processes, and text analytics. These tools enable machines to interpret, analyse and respond to complex inputs, making them highly valuable in data-driven environments such as journalism. In the context of journalism, AI is increasingly reshaping content creation and editorial workflows. Nwanyanwu & Nwanyanwu (2021) highlight the emergence of "media robots" capable of generating full news articles within minutes, a development that enables newsrooms to compete in an era dominated by real-time information dissemination. These intelligent systems enhance journalistic productivity by organising, analysing, and publishing information at unprecedented speeds. By identifying and learning from patterns in structured data, AI algorithms assist journalists in sorting through vast quantities of information efficiently while maintaining editorial coherence.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) includes a wide range of tools and technologies, such as natural language creation and processing, recognising speech, machine learning, deep learning platforms, fingerprinting, robotic process automation and text analytics (Ali & Hassoun, 2019). These technologies support a wide array of applications across different sectors, significantly enhancing operational efficiency, content production, and decision-making processes. AI is anticipated to have a profound impact on multiple facets of society, including the global economy, healthcare systems, education and climate change response. The global spending on Artificial Intelligence was projected to reach \$77.6 billion by 2022, reflecting its growing influence across industries (Takar, 2018).

In Africa, AI development is increasingly geared towards addressing practical and localised challenges. Major advancements are expected to focus on improving sectors such as healthcare, agriculture, and telecommunications, while also fostering the development of AI talent and promoting data security and regulation. Additionally, the deployment of AI is seen as a tool to combat misinformation, particularly across digital platforms (Qin, 2021; Nayebare, 2019).

A recent phenomenon. Its application in radio broadcasting dates back to the 1960s, when early forms of automation began to emerge. This evolution was the development of software capable of managing radio channel streams autonomously. These systems, often referred to as radio automation software, operate through algorithmic frameworks that can detect and manage programming sequences,

determining, for instance, when voice content or music should be broadcast (Qin, 2021). Such innovations laid the groundwork for AI-driven content scheduling and delivery, which are now integral components of modern broadcast operations.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be classified based on its capabilities and functionalities. Hintze (2016) identifies machine learning algorithm as central units of AI, noting that these technologies are increasingly surpassing human ability in ways that are transforming industries, including journalism, healthcare, and finance. AI systems can be further categorised into the following distinct classes: For instance, this form of Artificial intelligence is mostly used in autonomous vehicles, which track other cars' speeds and directions to make short-term driving decisions (Zhang, 2023). Kray (2018) compares this to human drivers who rely on past driving experiences to navigate traffic scenarios, though the AI does so in a more constrained and predefined manner.

Scholars across developing regions have examined the opportunities and challenges AI presents to journalism. Ali & Hassoun (2019) investigated AI and automated journalism, finding that while the technology raises professional and ethical questions—such as transparency, fairness, bias and data quality—it does not constitute a direct threat to professional journalism. Rather, they argue AI enhances journalistic work by supporting accuracy and efficiency. Similarly, José, César & Martín (2020) explored the Spanish media ecosystem and highlighted the transformative impact of AI on news production and consumption. Their qualitative study revealed that AI not only extends automated text to audio-visual content but also restructures business models and strengthens audience engagement.

In line with these findings, Sa'ad & Talat (2020) focused on the broader implications of robotics and AI for journalism. Their results indicated that while AI currently contributes to 15% of reporting and 9% of editorial work globally, it is unlikely to replace journalists. Instead, the technology is viewed as complementary, supporting timeliness, accuracy, and efficiency. Jamil (2022), in a study on Pakistani newsrooms, underscored the barriers to adopting AI, noting challenges in diffusion and implementation. This reflects the realities of resource-constrained environments where technological innovation is often gradual.

Further evidence from Portugal and Kenya provides more nuanced perspectives. Canavilhas (2022), through a survey of sports media decision-makers, examined current uses and expectations of AI. Findings suggest cautious optimism, with AI primarily viewed as a tool to streamline routine tasks. Similarly, Kioko, Booker, Chege & Kimweli (2022), through a multi-case study involving BBC-Africa and Radio Africa Group, confirmed optimism among journalists in Kenya about AI's potential. They identified key application areas such as tracking social media content and curating trending topics.

Overall, studies from developing contexts suggest that AI is reshaping journalism by automating routine tasks, diversifying content formats, and influencing newsroom structures. However, barriers related to ethics, resource capacity and organisational adaptation persist.

In Nigeria, empirical studies reveal both growing awareness and cautious adoption of AI in journalism. Guanah, Obi & Ginikachukwu (2020), through a content analysis of national newspapers, found that coverage of AI was limited, with most stories presented visually rather than editorially. This indicated low prioritisation of AI discourse within mainstream media. Complementing this, Okiyi & Nsude (2021) emphasised the

need for Nigerian newsrooms to embrace AI in order to remain competitive, although adoption remains slow due to infrastructural and ethical concerns.

Several empirical studies highlight awareness levels among journalists. Udoh, Nsude & Oyeleke (2021), surveying registered journalists in Ebonyi State, found high awareness of AI for news production. Similarly, Guanah, Agbanu & Obi (2021) showed that journalists in Benin City perceive AI-driven applications as improvements over manual reporting. At the same time, Nwanyanwu & Nwanyanwu (2021) revealed that while AI is augmenting newsroom tasks—such as fact-checking, personalisation, and investigative reporting—journalists remain hesitant, reflecting broader ethical and cultural reservations.

Other studies highlight perceptions about readiness and professional implications. Okocha & Ola-Akuma (2022) observed that although Nigerian journalists acknowledge robot journalism, many believe the public is not prepared for its adoption. This finding resonates with broader societal resistance to automation. Bello, Ishola & Umeaku (2023), in a survey of journalists in Lagos and Kwara States, confirmed high awareness but limited adoption, citing concerns about creativity and professional integrity. Lawal (2024) extended this discussion by focusing on job security, concluding that while journalists in Katsina State are highly aware of AI, acquiring AI-related skills is crucial to safeguard their roles in an evolving media environment.

Taken together, Nigerian studies demonstrate that awareness of AI is widespread among journalists, yet adoption is slow and shaped by ethical concerns, infrastructural challenges and perceptions of audience readiness. While journalists recognise AI's potential to augment their work, hesitancy persists, pointing to the need for further sensitisation, capacity building and contextual adaptation.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT), created in 2003 by Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis, is used in this study. The technology adoption model, the theory of planned behaviour and the innovation diffusion theory are just a few of the eight well-known theories of technology adoption that are incorporated into UTAUT, which functions as a comprehensive model. According to Ali & Hassoun (2019), the theory was created to offer a cohesive explanation of the major factors influencing people's intentions and behaviours with regard to the adoption of new technologies.

According to Venkatesh, Morris & Davis (2003), UTAUT identifies four core constructs that influence the acceptance and use of technology:

1. Performance Expectancy: the extent to which a person thinks that utilising a specific technology would improve results or performance at work.
2. Effort Expectancy: How simple it is to use the technology.
3. Social Influence: How much a person thinks significant others think they ought to utilise the new technique.
4. Facilitating Condition: The perceived organisational and technological infrastructure that supports the application of the technology is known as the "facilitating conditions."

These constructs are moderated by factors such as age, gender, experience and whether the technology usage is voluntary or mandatory. UTAUT has been widely

applied in various professional settings to predict and explain user acceptance and behaviour toward emerging technologies (Ward, 2021). This theory is particularly relevant to this study as it places the viewpoints of journalists inside a tried-and-true model of technology adoption by utilising the UTAUT framework. It enables a methodical investigating of their opinions regarding the utility, usability, social acceptability and institutional backing of AI in broadcasting. Additionally, this theoretical foundation offers an organised framework for analysing results and connecting them to more general conversations about the use of technology in the broadcast media.

Methodology

This study employed a qualitative research design, chosen for its strength in generating rich, in-depth insights from information-rich participants. Qualitative inquiry was considered appropriate because it facilitates the exploration of complex social phenomena in their natural settings rather than relying on numerical generalisations. As Denzin & Lincoln (cited in Ward, 2021) explain, qualitative research allows phenomena to be examined as they unfold in real life, enabling interpretation through participants' lived experiences. Similarly, Joubish (2011) emphasises that the purpose of qualitative research is to uncover underlying reasons, motivations and meanings.

The research population comprised broadcast journalists in Ilorin who were registered members of the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ), Kwara State Chapter. According to the NUJ register, a total of 82 broadcast journalists were officially recognised in the state at the time of the study. This group provided the accessible population for the research.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select respondents from the population. Purposive sampling was appropriate because the study targeted information-rich participants with direct experience of the phenomenon under investigation—namely, the perspectives of journalists in Ilorin on the implications of artificial intelligence for broadcast industry in Kwara State. From the 82 registered broadcast journalists, 11 were purposively selected across three radio stations (Midland FM, Sobi FM and Unilorin FM) and two television stations (Kwara TV and NTA Ilorin). Although the researcher initially proposed 13 informants, data collection concluded at 11 respondents once saturation was reached and no new insights were emerging. In-depth interviews served as the primary data collection method. This choice was informed by Jamshed (2014), who asserts that interviews are particularly useful in qualitative research because they provide opportunities for participants to articulate their views freely and in detail. The interviews allowed the researcher to capture nuanced perspectives and professional concerns about the integration of artificial intelligence in Nigerian journalism, an area that remains underexplored. Conducting the interviews across both radio and television stations ensured diversity in participants' experiences and enhanced the contextual richness of the findings.

Data Presentation and Discussion of Findings

Result were analysed and discussed in the following ways:

Theme 1: Negative Implications of AI on Journalism

This theme addresses the perceived drawbacks of AI integration into journalism, with insights grouped into the following sub-theme:

Figure 1: Negative Implications of AI on Journalism

Sub-theme 1.1: Impact on Job Roles and Skills

Job Displacement and Redefined Roles

Several participants expressed anxiety about AI's potential to replace human roles in newsrooms. They feared that increasing reliance on automated systems may render some journalistic roles obsolete. Participants also anticipated a shift from traditional reporting duties to more interpretive and analytical tasks, as suggested by Diakopoulos (2019).

“AI might make journalists lazy... Instead of using it as a support tool, many will begin to rely on it entirely, which may undermine credibility.” – Inf. MFM2

Loss of Investigative Rigor

Participants expressed worries that the convenience of AI tools could lead to a decline in investigative journalism. There was a concern that journalists may become complacent, opting for machine-generated content over in-depth research and original reporting.

Sub-theme 1.2: Ethics and Accountability

Erosion of Originality and Credibility

Many informants noted that AI might discourage journalists from crafting original content. The perception that machines could perform substantial parts of the journalistic process risks undermining authenticity and credibility.

“The challenges I foresee... [are] that it might kill originality. It will make journalists less dedicated and less credible.” – Inf. UFM8

Ethical Oversight and Manipulation Risks

Participants expressed concerns about potential misuse of AI, including bias in algorithms, misinformation, and the lack of ethical standards in automated reporting. These concerns underscore the urgent need for regulatory frameworks and continuous ethical training for journalists.

Theme 2: The Future of Journalism and AI Integration

This theme explores how journalists envision their evolving roles in the context of AI integration.

Figure 2: Future of Journalism and AI Integration

Role Transformation and Skill Adaptation

Emerging Analytical and Interpretive Functions: Participants envisioned that as AI increasingly takes over repetitive newsroom tasks, journalists will need to transition into more analytical and interpretive roles. Rather than being reduced to mere data gatherers, they anticipate their future responsibilities will demand contextualisation, human judgement, and critical storytelling.

Diversification and Accessibility of Media Work: At the same time, respondents noted that AI may democratise media production, lowering barriers of entry for individuals without formal journalistic training. As Inf. UFM8 highlighted, "AI will increase involvement in journalism and broadcasting by making it more accessible to a wider range of people." This suggests optimism that AI could broaden participation in journalism, though it simultaneously raises questions about quality control and professional standards.

Need for Balance and Human Oversight

Preserving the Human Element: Across the interviews, there was a clear consensus that despite AI's efficiency, human creativity and judgement remain indispensable. Participants stressed that AI should augment rather than replace journalists' contributions, ensuring that the emotional and ethical dimensions of reporting are preserved.

Call for Training and Policy Frameworks: Finally, respondents advocated for deliberate capacity-building and regulation. They argued that continuous training is essential to prepare journalists for an AI-driven future, while national policy frameworks are needed to ensure ethical use of AI in newsrooms. This reinforces the dual narrative observed in the data: AI is both a powerful enabler and a potential disruptor, and its integration requires careful balance between innovation and oversight.

Conclusion

This study concludes that journalists in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria, regard Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a revolutionary instrument in the broadcasting sector, presenting both advantageous and detrimental effects on their profession. Although AI can augment processes through the enhancement of news creation, data analysis, and audience interaction, it also poses considerable hurdles. Journalists recognise that AI may automate repetitive operations, hence accelerating and enhancing the news production process. Many voice apprehensions regarding the increasing dependence on AI, which may reduce human engagement in essential domains such as investigative journalism, creativity, and decision-making. Thus, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Broadcasting organisations should invest in regular training programmes for journalists to enhance their understanding of AI tools and their application in compromising journalistic integrity.
2. Journalists should embrace AI as a complementary tool to improve efficiency and accuracy in their work, while maintaining a critical approach to ensure ethical standards are upheld.
3. The Nigerian government and regulatory bodies should indicate clear guidelines and policies for the use of AI in the broadcasting industry to prevent the spread of misinformation and promote responsible journalism.

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